

THE IMPACT OF BABY WALKERS ON THE NEUROPSYCHOMOTOR DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issue of the impact of baby walkers on children's neuropsychomotor development. Its scientific relevance lies in the need to discuss ways of providing comprehensive care to children in the sensorimotor development phase. Its social relevance lies in the opportunity to provide a broad public with scientific knowledge and discussions about the negative impact of this device on children's entire physical structure, influencing creative performance, learning and problem-solving ability. This is a subject of extreme scientific relevance and public interest, with few studies taking a holistic approach to it. This is a bibliographical research, based on traditional authors on the subject of childhood and supported by extensive observation of babies in the sensorimotor development phase, at different socioeconomic levels. The baby walker, even though it is a very old device in human history and is widely accepted by parents because it provides comfort to them and not to the children, is still an object that poses great risk to users, such as accidents and traumas, which can be fatal and prevent the healthy and regular development of children, both physically and cognitively, intellectually and creatively, interfering in the process of building children's autonomy. We sought to describe the situations of risk and deformations that it can cause to the child's body structure, as well as possible future problems related to resistance, considering that the absence of physical exercises that strengthen the bones and the cardiac and pulmonary muscles that the child would naturally have to do until reaching the stage where he or she can walk upright is no longer performed.

Keywords: Baby walker. Phylogenetic development. Neuropsychomotor development. Strategies for overcoming natural challenges.

INTRODUCTION

The psychomotor development of any human being, especially in childhood, represents a very complex process, particularly for the individual themselves, because a whole neurological mechanism linked to the maturation of the mechanical structure is applied as a natural procedure, a kind of phylogenetic inheritance. As long as adults don't interfere by trying to accelerate these actions and/or overprotect children, the whole process happens in the most harmonious and intelligent way possible. The individual themselves seeks the tools to help them develop and overcome the difficulties that arise as they begin to explore their environment, starting from the particular to the global, from the bedroom to the backyard, the street, the neighborhood, and so on, first relying on the security of their parents through their company, then doing so alone or in the company of others.

This entire process unfolds in a simple way for an observer at a distance, because it is inherent to humans. Complementing this reasoning, Maslow refers to the human being, seeking to understand them in their broadest, deepest, and most complex constitution, arguing that, "each of us has an essential inner nature, biologically grounded, which is, to a certain extent, 'natural,' intrinsic, given, and, in a certain limited sense, invariable or, at least, invariant. [*And*], the inner nature of each individual is, in part, uniquely his own and, in part, universal in the species. [*Thus*], it is possible to study this inner nature scientifically and discover its constitution (not invent, but discover)" (Maslow, 1962, p. 27).

From this initial explanation, it is already possible to see that, when referring to the issue involving human psychomotor development, one is addressing highly complex neurological issues that are independent of human will, whether to accelerate or suppress them. This reveals that both types of intervention only hinder the natural individual performance predetermined by *Physis* for each species, which has already determined this procedure itself. It is at this point that the scientific discussion about the baby walker arises, as an instrument that negatively interferes with the child's motor development. This is precisely because, by not allowing the child to go through the natural phases of psychomotor development, it produces, as a result, a weakened adult in several ways, ranging from bone configuration to cardiorespiratory potential, diaphragmatic strength, and potential future spinal problems, considering that the child will walk crookedly and suffer distortions in leg alignment due to the angle created by the device.

An even more serious problem arises: during the natural process of psychomotor development, nature has prioritized the strengthening of the upper structures that protect the *most vital organs* of the human body, such as the heart and lungs [*this is also true for all animal*

species, not just humans], given that this is where the greatest concentration of bone plate density and size is found, as well as very strong, rigid musculature. When a child is allowed to use a walker, they stop strengthening this musculoskeletal structure [*in particular*] and instead use their legs, which neither strengthens their muscles nor allows for the production of cellular maturation synapses on the scale that nature has deemed ideal for their age group, *potentially* delaying osteoporotic maturation in the lower limbs.

The most interesting aspect of neuropsychomotor development in children is that, along with it, they also develop strategies to overcome challenges. Careful and attentive empirical observation reveals that they don't always expect adults to guide them through the process, often only seeking initial help and allowing them to continue, even if they make mistakes, fall, and try to get up on their own, using creative resources to overcome the natural barriers imposed by age and lack of muscle strength. This is the most significant aspect, because in the process, they create their autonomy and, to a certain extent, their independence.

As a child overcomes these obstacles, their intelligence naturally strengthens. This is contrary to what would happen if an adult, through unnatural mechanical mechanisms, interfered, suppressing natural stages that developed throughout the evolutionary process of the species. The challenges inherent in existential processes and the will, coupled with the need to overcome them, represent the main mechanism for inducing the development of intellectual strategies. With the use of a baby walker, a child is prevented from going down stairs, for example. As soon as they experience and encounter a challenging difficulty, they develop a scheme that seems to have been taught by an adult and, at the same time, learn to climb them, using techniques they themselves create. Interestingly, a compassionate adult appears to help them reach the top of the stairs; however, what matters to the child is not overcoming the stairs as such; what they seek is overcoming the challenge, learning how to become intellectually stronger. Protecting children from the possibility of failure [*when they do not understand it this way*] “may result in a kind of overprotection which, in turn, implies a certain lack of respect for the integrity, intrinsic nature and future development of the individual” (MASLOW, 1962, p. 33). Thus, when discussing the adoption of an instrument that interferes with the development of children's motor skills, it becomes clear that its negative influence extends to the being as a whole, which is already presupposed in the understanding that it is impossible to analyze the human being by considering only isolated parts and classify this absurdity as science.

The baby walker is a device that should never have been built; because a logical and well-planned analytical discussion about infant neuropsychomotor development would suffice—something any caring mother is capable of describing in detail—and one would arrive

at the definitive conclusion that its use negatively interferes with the child's progress in exploring space and overcoming challenges that naturally and inherently exist in their development. According to data from the Brazilian Society of Pediatrics (SBP, 2025), this device is used by approximately 60 to 90% of children aged between six and fifteen months.

The late 20th and early 21st centuries sparked a range of discussions in which personal motivations take the place of truths. Although the infamous *baby walker* was created as early as the 14th century with the intention of encouraging children to stand upright, it is known under what conditions and for what reasons its creator was led to this. It can be presumed that it was to use children for work even earlier. However, nothing justifies the continued doubt about the need for freedom granted to babies so that they can fully develop neurologically and motorically, given medical advances and studies stemming from Psychoanalysis, which is based on Anthropology, leading Medicine to focus on the study and understanding of human beings, especially in childhood. The use of an instrument that reduces [*and, in some aspects, completely limits*] the process of deliberate exploration of space means direct losses to overall child development.

Modern life leads humans to an existence marked by the dynamism of adult activities, and at the same time, for this to be effectively consolidated, it is necessary to reduce [*or limit*] the level of children's activities. For this reason, creations like these remain active, and even with all the efforts of pediatricians and educators to clarify the risks and harms of such creations to the life of the individual as a whole, the battle can be considered a *Sisyphian task*.

This work aims to expand the scientific discussion on the use of baby walkers, presenting the direct and indirect harm that their use causes to children in their respective developmental stages, whether in the motor, intellectual, or neurological fields. The following problem situation serves as *the leitmotif* for the intellectual development of this research: in what ways and under what aspects does the baby walker harm the neuropsychomotor development of the child?

As a general objective, this essay aims to analyze how the use of baby walkers interferes with the overall development of the child. Specifically, it intends to explain infant neuropsychomotor development and discuss the impact of affectivity on infant neuropsychomotor development.

Regarding the neuropsychomotor development of the child

Humans, at birth, are the most defenseless creatures that exist when compared to other living beings belonging to the animal kingdom. It takes many months for them to learn rudimentary walking and to strengthen their osteocorporeal and muscular structure, a process that begins from the moment they are born. This reveals that a certain region of the brain is already responsible for this procedure, even though, in general, it is far from being fully mature, at least partially.

All the movements performed by the newborn are aimed at strengthening their muscles; for this to happen, mothers and caregivers simply need to take due care to always place the child on their back, since this position, in addition to allowing them... Eye contact with their parents, even if their vision is still blurry; however, the freedom to move around is what matters.

mummy swaddling applied to newborn babies is no longer common, it would have made a mummification artist from the Egyptian Pharaonic dynastic era envious; however, it is not impossible to find in everyday situations, although Pediatrics and Pedagogy have already condemned the practice; but there are always some parents deluded by the fantasy of turning their children into fashion showcases, extravagantly dressing them in clothes, hindering their wider movements and condemning them to a state of thermal *stress*.

While still very young, just a few days after birth, a child can be observed opening and closing their hands; this is a muscle-strengthening exercise. Since they don't have muscle tone throughout their arms, nor the strength to move them fully, their neurons send signals to the parts they can exercise, seeking to strengthen them and provide neurological command training. This leads to the production of synapse chains, helping to promote brain growth. Therefore, it is understood that allowing children free and wide-ranging movements helps in the development of their broader brain functions.

The first movement a baby makes, interpreted as an orientation to the sound of the mother's voice, searching for her, is, if observed and analyzed very accurately, actually an exercise of the spinal trunk muscles, strengthening them to the point of being able to keep the head firm and centered. Similarly, when a baby is lying on its back and rocks back and forth, contrary to common belief that it is trying to turn over in bed, it is exercising its thoracolumbar muscles, attempting to strengthen them. This is because the baby's brain knows it will depend on its spine for locomotion; therefore, a whole process of muscle tone maturation, which will have a direct impact on future developmental actions, is worked on in a perfect cadence, following a logical sequence determined by *Physis*, independently of human intervention—which, incidentally, is what hinders development most when carried out intransigently.

Every movement a baby makes is not disordered or because it is searching for something out of its reach, especially since it has no information in its brain that instigates the satisfaction of desires; it has just been born, it is still practically blind, without any logical orientation. In this sense, Vygotsky and Luria emphasize that, “only after a month and a half of age does the baby present coordinated eye movements; only from this moment will the child be able to move its gaze from one object to another and from one part of the object to another; and, as we know, it is precisely these coordinated eye movements that are the necessary condition for seeing. However, a one-and-a-half-month-old child still has almost minimal access to the visually perceived world; accommodation of the eyeball – adaptation to external stimuli – appears around two months. Absolutely correct recognition of faces comes between two and a half and three months, and we can consider that only at four or five months does the 'visible world' become accessible to the child” (Vygotsky & Luria, p. 156).

Based on the clarification provided by the aforementioned researchers, it can be deduced that the eye movements babies make are, likewise, exercises to strengthen the eyeball muscles, and similarly, when they kick their legs, this act is an exercise to strengthen the muscle tone of the lower limbs. Thus, the entire body is being prepared for the development of the osteocorporeal musculature through simple actions. Because they lack linguistic articulation, their behavior must be interpreted and described so that interventions can be made when necessary; because reality has shown that the less adults interfere, the greater the chances of the child exhibiting healthy and full development.

As the child's trunk gains strength, they are able to sit up, turn their whole body, and look in the direction of sounds. Gradually, they begin to practice standing and start seeking support to help them with this task. During this period, they begin to crawl around the house, which strengthens two basic and extremely important functions. The first is exercising the dorso-thoracic musculature, which includes the maturation processes of the cardiac, smooth, and striated muscles, the respiratory system, especially the diaphragm, and blood circulation as a whole. It is observed that a range of organs and activities are put into full motion, each responsible for a vital function in the future, with greater demands depending on the chosen professional activity. However, the protection of the heart and lungs is a phylogenetic condition in all known species. This is evident from the fact that, primitively, domestic animals [especially pigs and cattle] had a much more prominent carcass in the thoracic region, and humans are no different, maintaining a much wider body span in this area.

Wild animals like lions, tigers, elephants, and rhinoceroses, since they are not of interest to humans for food [yet], maintain this primitive conformation of asymmetrical shape between

the front and rear parts. This is because, in the wild, battles between belligerents take place face to face, with attacks occurring directly on the heart. Among humans, when they are in wrestling rings, one only needs to observe which region of the body receives the most blows and punches to understand why *Physis* is so concerned with strengthening this musculature.

The second issue under analysis is that the crawling motion is not simply performed by dragging the lower limbs as if they were inert; they do not yet have sufficient tone to support the body's weight, nor the conditions for motor balance. But, by walking through spaces, crawling also strengthens the muscles of the legs and feet, not just exploring space. The child's psychic interest is a set of actions, each determined by the need to become autonomous and independent, and the most ridiculous thing one can see is how adults translate all the instinctive effort of the child into complex abstract actions, impossible to perform due to the neurological development of the child who, like all species, still in its initial phase, has the aspiration of survival above all else.

From a phylogenetic interpretive approach, children represent the most original phase of the human species, the phase in which they did not yet possess the elements that made them individuals endowed with analytical, interpretive, deductive, and synthetic capacity—to clarify, speech and logical reasoning. However, an unknown force endowed them with potentialities that, in themselves, allowed them to become capable of understanding the universe around them and, in their exploration to try to understand it, generated abstraction and other neurological elements such as attention, memory, and the perception of absence in some individuals—a term expressed here in an extremely generic way.

As the neurological system matures and overall muscle tone strengthens, the child is able to sit up and makes the first efforts to try to stand, which they are unable to do due to insufficient strength in these limbs. Therefore, they begin to look for objects to help them in this endeavor, a situation in which the family plays an important role in helping the child to stand and take their first steps, always being aware that if they let go, they will fall.

Proportionally to the advancement of this neurophysiological maturation process, the child discovers that by holding onto walls and furniture, they can walk upright and, unconsciously, risk letting go of their hands when near another individual who could assist them in case of a possible fall. Thus, inexplicably, because they lack the capacity for speech to explain the phenomenon, they apply a law of physics, in which, as they accelerate their pace, their equilibrium improves, allowing them to perform the famous little runs between one object and another. How they calculate the exact distance to apply this empirical mechanical principle will

always remain a mystery, because whoever could explain it neither speaks nor possesses the cognitive capacity to consciously process the dynamics of the action.

What is most striking about this whole process is that human physiological maturation begins in the brainstem, where it develops physical exercise strategies to mechanically strengthen it, eventually reaching the lower limbs and feet, where more dynamic and elaborate strategies are employed to make them strong and resilient. This also reveals that human libidinal energy is, in the first moments of extrauterine life, entirely directed towards structuring the physical condition; only after this consolidation, which the brain understands as the mastery of the ability to walk on two legs, does it advance to abstract psychological areas.

This finding suggests that delays in physical-motor development may hinder the development of abstract thought, a process commonly known as the development of intelligence [*both concrete and abstract*]. Alternatively, could delayed motor development be directly related to various neurological problems? If so, the retardation in the development of osteoporotic musculature signals potential neurological damage in children's brains, which may have been caused by congenital diseases such as syphilis, adrenoleukodystrophy, microfecalia , mineral and vitamin deficiencies during gestation, or by mechanical accidents during childbirth, among other hypothetical situations such as birth anoxia, eclampsia, ingestion of placental fluid, and delayed birth time.

All this suggests that there is a part of the brain that is already fully formed at birth, which could well be the psychic instance that Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) called the *unconscious*. Eugênio Mussak (2000) refers to this cerebral instance as the *reptilian brain* , because it is a structure common to all living beings, originating in reptiles, which predates humans and exhibits similar behavior, so as not to use the expression *identical behavior here* .

In the human species, "the brain at birth is only 23% the size of the adult brain. Rapid growth continues during the six years following birth, and full growth is not completed before the age of twenty-three" (Morris, 1967, p. 22), making humans the latest creatures in terms of neurological maturation. In this process, many essential functions will only be achieved after certain specific ages, and there may be situations of precocity and/or retardation without either harming the existence of the individual and their social well-being once they have reached adulthood.

The fact that a human being, in their first moments of life, possesses a brain volume equivalent to little more than one-fifth of that of an adult, allows us to deduce that all their potential is directed towards aspects they consider essential, such as developing the sensory organs, since this theoretically guarantees them a greater chance of survival in the world. In this

way, the brain itself is aware that it needs to obey the instinctive parameters pertinent to the species, understanding this condition from what the Master of Vienna reveals about the human phylogenetic aspect, in which, for him, “an instinct would be an impulse, present in every living organism, tending towards the restoration of a previous state, which that living being had to abandon due to the influence of disturbing external forces, a kind of organic elasticity or, if you prefer, the expression of the inertia of organic life” (Freud, [1920] 2006, p. 28-9).

The expression “*organic life*” to which Sigmund refers may well have been extracted from the thought of E. Durkheim (1858-1917), as a veiled critique of the contemporary lifestyle, in which the development of motor skills was no longer as important as it was in primitive times, when man was still the most fragile and, at the same time, the least dangerous being in nature. However, the essence of a being is the expression of what it represents as part of a species, and in this, all that it possesses of genetic inheritance is revived through the individual and their behavior; with this, one arrives at the conclusion that, by observing the entire behavioral process of a single member, one has the objective possibility of clarifying and describing the evolutionary trajectory of the species to which it belongs.

What this discussion has sought to convey is an understanding of the process of developing children's psychomotor skills. As analyzed, this process occurs from the brain to the lower limbs in a linear and directed cycle until it is realized, determining the muscular structure that will then continue to develop according to the mechanical activities performed. This process happens very naturally, leaving room for the brain to dedicate efforts to developing aspects related to cognition and experiences through contact with the environment. All this seems to be so that, from the realization of this event, the brain will enable developmental endeavors directed towards the formation of the limbic system [responsible for abstract emotions] and the formation of the cortical system [*directly responsible for the formation of consciousness, abstract learning, and creativity, aiming at overcoming challenges*]. Thus, it can be inferred from all this that the longer it takes for this first phase to be completed efficiently and effectively, the more it will delay the child's intellectual development.

Here, at this inflection point from mechanical development to abstract development, the child will need maximum freedom to explore the environment using their body without any kind of impediment from artificial objects, because they will have to use their creativity to overcome some natural barriers, even if they don't succeed; but at least they should try, since failure in the endeavor is interpreted by the child as a challenge to be overcome at some other time, using some strategy that allows them to achieve their goal.

If a child is prevented from employing her own strategies by some instrument she cannot free herself from, this prevents her from attempting to satisfy her desire again. This is because she first needs to free herself from an object that limits her ability to perform actions related to objects that would somehow help her in her objective conquest. This condition of being prevented from carrying out self-directed interventions will affect the development of her intellect, although it is impossible to specify to what extent; however, the attempt to reach an object, the satisfaction of a desire, and even the failure to realize it, induces the production of subjective ideas about how to overcome such obstacles, often creating situations in which adults become this alternative. However, being confined to a device that almost completely restricts the child's freedom makes this *almost* impossible; this is why, from now on, we intend to argue against the use of baby walkers, as they limit and even prevent the biomechanical development of children in the most critical phase of their neuropsychomotor potential.

According to the Brazilian Society of Pediatrics (SBP, 2025), baby walkers delay a child's psychomotor development. This has been proven by observing that babies who use walkers take longer to stand and walk without support. This is because the entire mechanical process of developing skills, achieved through effort and the creation of overcoming tactics, did not occur at the time considered by the child's brain as the ideal moment, when overcoming the challenges of a given stage leads to another more challenging and therefore more important one. Furthermore, these babies confined to walkers crawl less and have lower scores on psychometric development tests. Physical exercise is greatly hampered by the use of walkers because, although they provide more mobility and speed, the child needs to expend less energy with them than trying to reach what interests them with their own arms and legs.

With this approach, what we have is a strict clarification of how much the walker hinders the child's normal motor and cognitive development. By not allowing them to advance in solving their problems, it limits their creative process, which, to adults, may seem the most obvious thing to do in a given situation. When challenged, the child learns a series of things that are extremely necessary for their future life, without even realizing it, because, as Freud (1856-1939) rightly pointed out, the over-existence given to human beings causes them to repeat all their discoveries and developmental nuances in the next existence, which is characterized as ontogenetic development. Contrary to what has been taken as truth—that children should be *taught* an infinite number of things in their early childhood—the correct approach is *to allow* them access to this range of things and let their curiosity lead them to request learning through an adult.

How does a baby walker interfere with a child's neuropsychomotor development?

The issue of the influence of baby walkers on a child's neuropsychomotor development is a subject that, at first glance, deserves deeper questioning: based on what medical, pedagogical, and developmental parameters does someone create an instrument that, instead of enabling the child's broad freedom, actually restricts it even further?

It is very common, especially in Brazil, to create mechanisms and instruments aimed at children without any prior study to clarify their advantages and disadvantages, with only heated defenses claiming that the use of the instrument will not affect the individual's development in any way, and the most frightening thing about all this is that nobody [*or almost nobody, professionals in related fields*] protests against this infamous invention.

When Skinner (1904-1990) created his infamous *Skinner Box* (1938) and subsequently used his daughter as a guinea pig, his intention was to prevent her from interfering with his studies. When questioned about whether this experience had harmed her cognitive development in any way, protecting her father's image prevailed, and her response was an emphatic " *no* ." Similarly, one might assume that the invention of the baby walker stemmed from a *concerned father* who didn't want to worry about where his child was going around the house, considering that this device drastically limits a child's freedom to explore the home environment.

Using a baby walker prevents children from following their normal, linear developmental process. Each stage of development serves as a foundation for the next, and a lack of consolidation in the previous stage will lead to delays in maturational progress, thus affecting the child's overall development.

Generally, children are placed in baby walkers when they begin to crawl, a crucial time for strengthening their thoracic trunk, diaphragm, biceps muscles, forearms, and enhancing respiratory capacity. This brief overview alone shows that its use negatively affects human biomechanical development in the long term. Another detail is that, as the child crawls around the home, they are already exercising their legs, promoting joint articulation and building muscle tone in the nerves, muscles, and bones.

When using a walker, the legs are suspended, with only the feet touching the ground. Since the feet do not yet have sufficient strength to support the body's weight, the child uses a method to reduce the weight-bearing capacity, already influenced by the shape imposed by their position in the device. This leads to gait defects, causing uneven wear on shoes (inward or outward), and consequently, spinal problems such as cervical deviations or possibly herniated discs.

This happens because, naturally, the child goes through developmental stages where they are born with legs in a pincer shape, a situation that resolves itself by around two years of age, and then transitions to an X shape, a natural situation that resolves completely and without interference by around seven years of age. The problem is that the walker represents a negative and inappropriate interference because it prevents the child's *physis* and brain from performing their work in an orderly and free manner, following phylogenetic patterns.

When a child is still crawling, they face an enormous and seemingly insurmountable challenge in the house: stairs. Faced with them, they feel incapable of climbing or descending them, although they try and even risk it; but their immediate interest lies in climbing the steps, because this provides a panoramic view of their surroundings from above. As they manage to stand, holding onto objects around the house, such as chairs, boxes, and even the steps of the stairs, they begin to make their first attempts to climb them, first forcing their body as a whole, which can be understood as an exercise to strengthen the entire dorso-thoracic region. Then, they make their first attempts to place their right leg on the step, regardless of whether they are left-handed, and as soon as they overcome the first step, they extend the action to the second, and so on, until they overcome the challenge.

Once you reach this level, you seek to explore the environment, making it familiar, and upon completing your journey, you reverse the path, having to develop a strategy to overcome the obstacle. Here is another challenge that demands an enormous amount of creative energy, but which, without one being able to understand how it elaborates the reasoning, applies the opposite, reverse principle; and if, to climb the ladder, you used your arms as support and then made coordinated movements with your legs, now you follow the same path, but in reverse, supporting yourself on the step with your body and then making movements with your legs to feel secure and apply it to the next steps until you finish your journey.

Once the child has developed sufficient muscle tone to no longer rely on supporting themselves entirely on the steps of the ladder, they begin climbing on all fours, supporting themselves with their hands flat on the steps while their legs are upright on the same steps. Once this is successfully performed, they repeat the exercise until they are confident in its unrestricted application. After overcoming this stage, they begin climbing the ladder using the wall for support; that is, they climb standing upright, but securing themselves with their hands on the wall. All of this is done without the encouragement or direct help of any adult.

From the moment a child is confined to a walker, all these real opportunities for creative development and attempts to overcome obstacles, using their own capacity for analysis, interpretation, and synthesis of the opportunities presented to them, are thrown into inertia. To

make matters worse, these conditions are physical, extremely natural determinations that, once lost, will no longer be available to them because these are not abstract situations; they are mechanical, biomechanical in the strict sense.

Similarly, walkers cause delays in gait development; because, as explained above, the stages of *Genu Varum* (bow-leggedness) and *Genu Valgum* (knock-knees) are natural conditions of childhood that correct themselves, provided there is no human intervention, except in cases where it proves necessary. The fact that the child remains upright when they should be strengthening their muscle tone through crawling, without the proper maturation of their osteocorporeal structure, leads their brain to a state of incomprehension about what to do, since an entire phylogenetic developmental process has been distorted.

Consequently, with this undue intervention, actions aimed at creative thinking are also not highlighted, which can affect cognitive and intellectual development, seriously damaging children's creative protagonism and causing delays in the intellectual sphere. This can lead to cases where mental age is below chronological age, hindering abstract learning upon entering regular schools, such as linguistic deficits, and delays in acquiring literacy skills, both linguistic and mathematical and logical.

What becomes clear from this explanation is that the device, in addition to directly causing adverse reactions to the child's biomechanical development, what it prevents in terms of instinctive brain construction reflects on the entire process of abstract elaboration that follows as organic developmental stages of the human being, which makes it an object to be avoided at all costs in a child's life, with no justification whatsoever that allows for the slightest room for contrary argument.

Up to now, the possibility of any type of domestic accident that can occur with or without the device has not been addressed; but when a child falls and is free of any restraint, they quickly crawl and settle down, asking for help or seeking someone to provide the necessary assistance. However, being restrained by the device, they may not always be able to free themselves, remaining for a relatively long time in a position that can be risky for their age and physical condition, because, as a rule, the use of this device by families is a search for parental freedom, through the limitation of the child's freedom in the physical space of the home.

The normal pattern of walking for a child, and even an adult human, is that the entire body mass is distributed evenly across the soles of the feet, as this distribution is perfectly in

line with height, mass distribution, and bone density. In the developmental process, this is part of a complex body scheme in which the foot is the last part of the body to be formed and to mature, respecting the entire maturation scheme of the brain-spinal system, trunk, and limbs (upper and lower).

With the use of baby walkers, a very serious problem occurs with the development of gait, which is that the child steps on the balls of their feet and, at most, on the area before their toes, preventing them from learning to support the entire sole of their feet when walking. This can lead to motor imbalances and a greater risk of tripping and falling, because it gives the impression that the motor balance center in the central nervous system becomes misaligned, with a tendency to propel forward.

This tendency leads to problems in the normal development of gait and, as it is characterized as an abnormal process of motor balance, what other natural biomechanical processes, inherent to human beings, might be affected by this anomaly caused by human interference? What is astonishing is the fact that simple observation is enough to detect abnormalities in the child's posture within that medieval machine of child destruction; yet, there are those who insist on claiming that any *possible* deviation will be corrected naturally as the child develops physically.

This is the crucial and most alarming point, because this is a phase for which there are no corrective mechanisms, as it is instinctive, phylogenetic, and produced by the brain itself following patterns completely unknown to humans and which, especially, do not depend on their intervention to follow parameters of harmonic perfection. The baby walker does nothing more than interfere, negatively, in the osteocorporeal development of the human being, affecting their entire existence.

Regarding the possibility of domestic accidents, stairs represent the main risk; however, what is not clear is that a child will never fall from them if they have the opportunity to explore the obstacle empirically. This is because they approach the stairs, look at their height, distance, and the level of the challenge, and after a meticulous analysis, decide whether or not to risk facing it. In this way, they don't give up, only postpone the undertaking in favor of their physical strength. This applies to both climbing and descending stairs.

Mounted on the spaceship designed for non-human creatures, the child's field of vision is altered, impairing their judgment of distances, spaces, direct and indirect risks, and even the possibility of accessing or overcoming the challenge. This causes them to bump into stairs when at the foot of them and fall when at the top, placing them at serious risk of death or accidents

that can lead to delays in motor development due to fear or insecurity regarding their own judgment of the situation.

When a child falls and gets hurt, through their own effort and attempt to overcome a challenge they set for themselves, once the pain subsides, they are already attempting the same endeavor again. Many adults don't understand this and wonder how the child wasn't traumatized or afraid. The answer is simple: they just made a miscalculation and, based on what they've learned since their last attempt, they've had time to recalculate and are ready for a new undertaking, one they are sure they will succeed at. In this sense, Maslow argues that, "the moment-to-moment developmental process is intrinsically rewarding and delightful, in an absolute sense. If they are not culminating experiences, at least they are experiences at the foot of the mountain, brief glimpses of absolute pleasure, which validate themselves as a full expression of the self, small moments of Being" (Maslow, 1962, pp. 186-7).

What the author wants to make clear is that the challenges faced by each developing being must be overcome through their own effort, which, far beyond being strictly physical, is cognitive in nature. Even if a child doesn't yet know how *to* express their thoughts, this doesn't mean they aren't being processed in their brain in some way that isn't *yet possible* to understand. Therefore, allowing children in the sensorimotor development phase to overcome their own tasks or communicate their interests to adults is a way to strengthen their creative capacity, as well as the emotional bond with their parents, teachers, and caregivers. And even when adult intervention is necessary, it's essential to explain *the* entire situation and why the child couldn't resolve it on their own.

Everything presented here leads to the understanding that it's not about overcoming an obstacle as if that were the end of a journey; the intrinsic understanding is that if one challenge can be overcome, all others that come in the future can also be overcome through individual effort. With this, the child is creating a world of possibilities for themselves, learning naturally to combat their anxiety in the face of challenges that, at first glance, seem impossible.

The mistake lies in adults attempting to define and reduce the child's world based on their own worlds and stereotypes produced from schizophrenic existential interpretations. The role of parents and other adults in a child's life is to support them according to what they cannot yet process; to provide them with what they need and desire to overcome the obstacles that nature has given them as part of their existence on the planet. Interferences in child development, however well-intentioned, should be carried out with great care and only in situations where there is no other option. this .

One of the most serious problems plaguing humanity today is the fact that there is a group of individuals who have taken theoretical knowledge as responsible for mastering the entire process, without having to observe the behavior of the object, analyze it in depth, and, based on hasty conclusions devoid of any plausible foundation, they are already giving results arbitrarily as if things happened by some untimely miracle. With the development of the baby walker, this is exactly what happened: someone who, obviously, is not from the field of Pediatric Medicine, much less from the field of Pedagogy and Psychomotricity, decided to create something that helps parents keep children under control and began to spread the idea that it helps the developing child walk faster because, by putting them upright, the brain would produce command synapses strengthening this aspect.

The problem is that all of this, besides being the result of preconceived ideas, has no empirical scientific basis whatsoever, and what careful observation has proven is that this instrument actually has the opposite effect, delaying motor development, gait, and consequently, cognition, affecting creativity, and putting the child at risk of accidents, some even serious and fatal. Family support is the best remedy for the child to progress in developing their entire neuropsychomotor scope.

Falk, in his book *Educating the First Three Years: the Lóczy experience* (2011), argues: “the activity of movement and free play – without the initiating or modifying participation of the adult – reinforces the special learning possibilities of the baby and young child that nothing else can replace” (p. 35).

What the author expresses through his speech is what has already been explained throughout this work: that the child seeks to solve challenges as a way of maturing their entire personality structure. This structure, during the early childhood developmental phase, is characterized by advancements in the sensorimotor system, and each movement performed has a pure and determined instinctive interest, preparing them for the next phases of their existence. The interference of an adult, which some unwary individuals may consider an act of love and protection, is in fact a negation of this, causing considerable losses to the dynamic pursuit of overcoming challenges through the child's own cognitive efforts, which involve analysis and interpretation of situations, albeit in a very rudimentary way.

The more welcoming the environment, the more the child will dare to explore it and take on challenges as an essential part of their life—routine situations that, once overcome, will lead them to seek out more challenging ones and even to repeat those already conquered, in order to ascertain their ability. Children's thinking is an enigma because of their inability to

verbalize it; however, careful observation reveals how things are processed in their intrinsic world.

CONCLUSION

What occurs in humans, from infancy to adulthood, is the maturation of the brain, which consequently leads to the conditioning of simple processes, making them complex because they undergo analysis and attempts at understanding. There is a systematic organization of all sensory organs, and the biological event itself begins to interfere in these processes. Piaget believed that human development is an inherent, unalterable, and evolutionary process of the species, distinguished by a series of phases and sub-phases or stages (Piaget, 1987). In this sense, each phase reflects a range of organizational points, which manifest themselves in a defined sequence within an approximate age period in continuous development. This sequence of biologically determined phases, described by Piaget, represented a milestone for subsequent studies on teaching and learning processes, making it possible to develop didactic and pedagogical work methods more consistent with each age.

Piaget (1896-1980) observed differences throughout the developmental period of children aged 0 and 2 years. The cognitive phases differ according to age, but development still occurs. Gradually, behaviors become more complex: movements and displacements that are initially centered on the body itself gain more perception and motor skills, enabling the child to discover new means of active experimentation, and also to invent them. It is noted that at this stage the child does not yet have an autonomous existence, has not yet acquired body permanence, which makes the coordination between vision and pressure very important. By pressure we understand the act of voluntarily reaching for an object and not the innate reflex of grasping with the hands what lightly touches the palm of the hand. The coordination between vision and pressure makes possible behaviors that can be truly qualified as intentional. Concrete actions, which are essential, are followed by internalized actions, that is, thought; It is suggested that infants possess an advanced level of intellectual behavior, including memory, and use it from the first days of their lives. However, "the memory of babies is fragile, referring to very simple events and situations, and the duration of the mnemonic trace is far from comparable to what it will have only a few years later" (Palacios, 1999, p. 88), because, as stated above, there is not enough brain organization to store data in a complex way as in the adult mind. Even the adult mind performs a process of selection/exclusion/deletion of very high density because otherwise the brain would not withstand the emotional load and energy expenditure.

Human brain maturation is a long-lasting biological process, lasting approximately until the age of 21, although some sources suggest it can extend to 24 years; therefore, the brains of newborns and even babies up to 2 years old are in an embryonic stage of development. From infancy onwards, children continuously strive to adapt or mold themselves to their environment. Through this process, they absorb the elements necessary to achieve their goals. In this pursuit, their brains expand their horizons of knowledge; simultaneously, their bodies also develop.

The process of cognitive maturation runs parallel to physical development, hence this stage is referred to as psychophysical. In other words, both instances occur in such a way that, as the body supports daily experiences, these experiences are introduced, even through the individual's interest in them or through intrinsic and extrinsic needs related to problem-solving and overcoming challenges.

Throughout this work, the role of the baby walker and its influence on the development of the child's neuropsychomotor aspect have been discussed with great emphasis. After intense argumentation, it can be concluded that its use hinders the entire process of building the human biological structure because it interrupts a natural process of advancement towards a self-defined situation, since it represents an individual repetition of an evolutionary instinctual mechanism to which the species has been subjected.

The aim was to describe the risk and deformity situations that can be caused to the child's body structure, as well as possible future problems related to resistance, considering that the absence of physical exercises to strengthen the bones and the cardiac and pulmonary muscles that the child would naturally have to do until reaching the stage where they can walk upright is not carried out.

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